

GEOLOGIC MAPPING OF MARE AUSTRALE REGION: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE EVOLUTION OF LARGE IMPACT BASINS A. Gao^{1,2}, L. Xiao¹, W. Iqbal², L. Wueller², C. H. van der Bogert² and H. Hiesinger^{2, 1}
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Introduction: Mare Australe comprises 248 discrete mare basalt units [1], forming a near-circular structure >880 km in diameter, centered at ~38.9°S, 93.0°E [2]. Its mare distribution has been associated to a possible pre-Nectarian Australe basin [3,4], though no definitive morphological evidence exists [5]. Gravity data reveal a degraded positive Bouguer anomaly in the northern portion of Mare Australe, suggesting an additional Australe North basin [6]. Multi-stage volcanic activity spans from 3.91 to 3.08 Ga [7,8], subdivided into four periods from late Nectarian to Eratosthenian [1]. In addition, increasing evidence indicates widespread ancient cryptomare deposits [9,10]. These observations point to a complex, poorly constrained geologic history, with unclear relationships between large basins and volcanism. This study maps the Australe region (58°E–130°E, 10°S–70°S) to provide new insights into the evolution of Mare Australe.

Methodology: A 1:500,000 scale geologic map was produced using LRO-WAC global mosaic [11], SLDEM2015 DEM [12], and Kaguya Multiband Imager data [13]. Mineralogy maps from [14,15] and GRAIL gravity data [16] were used to provide additional information. The map adheres to FGDC standards [17] and the stratigraphic framework of [18].

Preliminary Map Units: The geologic units within the study area have been classified into terra materials, basin material, plain materials and crater materials.

Figure 1: Geologic Map of the Mare Australe region, produced at a scale of 1: 500,000

Terra materials: The *pre-Nectarian terrain* (*pNt*) shows degraded, hummocky topography with 2–8 km high massifs formed by cumulative ancient basin materials. It forms an arcuate highland ridge across Mare Australe, with prominent (>5 km, ~25°) massifs

formed by multiple large impact events, probably including South-Pole Aitken basin and Australe North basin.

Basin materials: Large impact basins serve as key stratigraphic markers within the region. Among them, Australe basin is the most degraded one, expressed only as a subdued, partially mare-filled depression whose boundary cannot be confidently defined due to the lack of diagnostic morphologic and gravity signatures. The characteristics of other identifiable basins are described as follows.

Australe North basin: The Australe North basin exhibits a highly fragmented structure, partially intermingled with other ancient basins, complicating its identification. Gravity and topography analyses reveal a near-circular low-relief depression in northern Mare Australe, underlain by a positive Bouguer anomaly with a southwestern gap coinciding with the arcuate highland ridge. The anomaly was interpreted as the highly degraded mascon of Australe North basin. Massifs 2–3.5 km high along the depression edges, intersected by pre-Nectarian terra (*pNt*) material, likely represent the basin’s inner ring (~650 km). Scattered massifs across the highland ridge, encircled by ancient terrains, form a potential outer ring (~1150 km). These massifs are extensively mantled by impact ejecta, resulting in lower relief than the *pNt* massifs. Extensive burial by post-impact material prevents mapping of additional remnants, indicating that Australe North basin is among the oldest and most degraded large basins in this region.

Smythii Basin: The Smythii basin (872 km) preserves at least two recognizable basin rings with ~3 km relief. Although primary ejecta and secondary craters are no longer identifiable, the relatively well-preserved ring morphology suggests that Smythii is younger than the Australe North basin.

Milne Basin: The Milne basin (264 km diameter) preserves well-defined outer ring structures, whereas its inner ring is degraded but still traceable. Rim structures superpose the inferred Australe North inner ring. Its comparatively smoother basin floor, relative to the Smythii basin materials, suggests that Milne is among the younger pre-Nectarian impact basins in the region.

Nectaris Basin: The Nectaris basin (885 km diameter) is a multi-ring structure defines the boundary between the pre-Nectarian and Nectarian periods. Within the study area, Nectaris ejecta overlie the western flank of the Australe North basin, forming smooth plains and ghost craters. The Nectaris basin material is

characterized by abundant radial crater chains oriented toward the basin center.

Plain materials

Nrp: *Nectarian Rough plain units (Nrp)* occur in basin-related depressions. They exhibit rugged textures and degraded landforms, reflecting prolonged impact modification. Fresh craters (>2 km in diameter) expose mafic ejecta, suggesting the presence of cryptomare.

Ilp: *Imbrian light plain (Ilp)* units display smoother textures than rough plains but retain small-scale hummocky features and pervasive ballistic ejecta modification. They are concentrated in low-relief depressions within ancient highlands and large basins. The *Ilp* units may have formed through large-scale impact-related depositional processes since the Imbrian period.

UIlp: *Upper Imbrian light plains (UIlp)* are smoother and display lower crater densities than Imbrian light plains, suggesting a relatively younger surface age. They are concentrated on the floors of large craters. Their feldspathic spectral signatures indicate a composition dominated by mixed ballistic ejecta, impact melt, and late-stage volcanic materials.

INDp: The *Imbrian–Nectarian dark plain (INDp)* unit consists of mare basalt infilling intercrater plains within basin-floor depressions (e.g., Australe North and Balmer regions). Compared to adjacent dark plains, it displays higher crater density and albedo, indicating an older surface age. Geochemically, elevated plagioclase (~53%) and reduced FeO (~13%) contents suggest significant highland lateral contamination.

UIDp: The *Upper Imbrian dark plain (UIDp)* unit has a smooth surface, low albedo, and relatively high FeO content (~17%), with model ages of ~3.4–3.9 Ga. During this stage, basaltic materials also filled crater floors across Mare Australe, forming a near-circular assemblage of mare deposits.

Edp: The *Eratosthenian dark plain (Edp)* units have the lowest albedo and crater density among the dark plains, indicating late-stage regional volcanism. They are restricted to the northern study area, with absolute model ages of 2.9–3.2 Ga [8].

Crater materials

NpNc: The *Nectarian Pre-Nectarian Craters (NpNc)* consist of highly degraded craters with no continuous ejecta. They are heavily eroded and partly buried, widely modified by ballistic ejecta forming secondary crater chains and smooth plains. They represent the region's oldest recognizable craters.

Llc: The *Lower Imbrian craters* are characterized by relatively well-preserved crater rims. Their floors are generally filled with Imbrian mare and light plain materials, and their surfaces are heavily modified by numerous secondary craters, likely derived from younger Imbrian basins.

Ulc: The *Upper Imbrium craters* exhibit more well-preserved crater rims and recognizable ejecta blanket structures. Their degree of degradation is significantly lower than that of the *Llc* units, although secondary craters and erosional features from younger impact events are still observable on their surfaces.

Eic: *Eratosthenian Imbrian craters (Eic)* exhibit sharper crater rims than the *Ulc* units; however, their ejecta blankets are more degraded compared to those of younger craters. Therefore, they can be attributed to either the Imbrian or the Eratosthenian units. Some of the smaller *Eic* containing unrecognizable ejecta blankets are interpreted as secondary craters of large basins, such as Orientale basin.

Ec: *Eratosthenian craters (Ec)* display well-preserved impact crater morphologies with sharp crater rims. Their ejecta blankets are intact and clearly defined, exhibiting fresh and rough surface textures. However, no bright rays are observed.

Cc: *Copernican craters (Cc)* exhibit the most well-preserved and sharply defined crater morphologies, accompanied by fresh ejecta blankets. Bright rays are commonly observed surrounding these craters.

Conclusions: Our observations indicate that Mare Australe region underwent a complex geologic evolution, involving multiple large-impact basin modifications and multi-stage volcanism whose distribution is closely linked to basin structures. In particular, the stratigraphic relationships between the Australe North and South Pole–Aitken basins, as well as the distinct characteristics of different volcanic stages, warrant further investigation.

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